

What Drives the Expansion of Giant Ionized Shells Around Young Stellar Clusters?

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Abstract Stellar mechanical and radiation feedback play a fundamental role in the dynamics and structuring of the Interstellar Medium (ISM) in star forming galaxies. Here we discuss the impact that the two major forces, the mechanical and radiation pressure, provide on the star cluster wind-driven shells. We present the results of the calculations for a $10^5 M_{\odot}$ cluster embedded into a dense interstellar gas with $n_{ISM} = 10^4 \text{cm}^{-3}$ and conclude that radiation pressure may affect the inner structure and the dynamics of the wind-driven shell only during the earliest stages of evolution or if a significant fraction of the star cluster mechanical luminosity is dissipated or radiated away within the star cluster volume.

1 Introduction

Stellar feedback - the injection of radiation and mechanical energy by young massive stars - plays a fundamental role in the dynamics and structuring of the ISM in star forming galaxies. The thermalization of the mechanical energy provided by stellar winds and supernova explosions in compact and young stellar clusters leads to the development of a star cluster wind and this, in turn, to a strong shock which sweeps up the ambient gas into a dense shell that moves supersonically into the surrounding ISM. The theory of star cluster wind-blown bubbles was developed by Weaver et al. (1977). Different aspects of this theory have been discussed by many authors (see reviews by Tenorio-Tagle & Bodenheimer 1988; Bisnovaty-Kogan & Silich 1995).

The comparison of model predictions with observed shells led Oey (1996) to discover that in many small and intermediate size cases the observed radii are too small compared to the model predicted values (see however the discussion of the largest shells whose radii are comparable to the characteristic scale-height of the galactic gaseous disks in Tenorio-Tagle 1981; Silich et al. 2006).

The discrepancy between the classic wind-blown bubble model and the observed sizes and expansion velocities of the interstellar bubbles (the growth rate discrepancy or the missing wind problem) led to extensive debates and novel views on the problem. In a series of recent papers (Matzner 2002; Harper-Clark & Murray 2009; Lopez et al. 2011) it was suggested that the shocked cluster wind gas may leak from the bubble interior into the surrounding ISM and claimed that in such cases radiation pressure dominates the dynamics of the surrounding shells while Pellergrini, Baldwin & Ferland (2011) reached the opposite conclusion from their analysis of the ionization parameter distribution in the 30Dor region. Here we present the results of recent calculations and discuss how the stellar radiative feedback may affect the density/pressure distribution and the dynamics of wind-blown shells around young massive clusters.

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2 Input physics

We consider a young massive ($10^5 M_\odot$) star cluster embedded into a homogeneous ISM with a particle number density $n_{ISM} = 10^4 \text{ cm}^{-3}$ and temperature $T_{ISM} = 100 \text{ K}$. It is assumed that the star cluster mechanical luminosity is constant and equal to $L_{mech} = 10^{39} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$. The radiation feedback (the rate of ionizing photons, Q_0 , and the star cluster ionizing L_i and non-ionizing L_n luminosities) are calculated by means of Starburst99 synthetic model (Leitherer et al. 1999) with the standard Kroupa initial mass function and $0.1 M_\odot$ and $100 M_\odot$ as low and upper mass cutoffs, respectively. We use the Weaver et al. (1977) equations to calculate the radius of the star cluster wind-driven shell and the value of thermal pressure at the contact discontinuity which separates the shocked wind matter from the swept-up interstellar gas in the shell and Draine (2011) equations to calculate the distribution of density and thermal pressure in the shell exposed to the radiation from the central cluster. The results of the calculations are plotted then on a diagnostic diagram which allows one to decide if radiation pressure affects the shell dynamics significantly. A detailed discussion of the input parameters and main equations used in the simulation and the results of the calculations for more massive ($10^6 M_\odot$) clusters embedded into different ISM are presented in Martínez-González, Silich & Tenorio-Tagle (2014).

3 Results and discussion

Figure 1 presents the results of the calculations for two cases. In case A (the upper and middle left-hand panels) the shell expansion begins in the Weaver et al. energy-dominated mode. However a transition to the momentum-driven regime then occurs at $\sim 0.16 \text{ Myr}$ either due to strong radiative losses of energy in the shocked wind region or due to the gas leakage through holes in the shell, as suggested in the leaky bubble model (e.g. Matzner 2002).

Solid, dashed and dotted lines show the calculated density, thermal and ram pressure profiles in and around the wind-driven shell. The upper and middle panels on the right-hand column present the results of the calculations in the case with low star cluster heating efficiency (case B). These calculations are motivated by the possible strong losses of energy inside the star cluster volume and by the deviation of the mechanical energy input rate from the average value at the earliest stages of evolution. In this case we keep the values of L_i , L_n and Q_0 equal to those predicted by the Starburst99 synthetic model, but instead of using the average mechanical luminosity predicted for a $10^5 M_\odot$ cluster, we use an order of magnitude smaller value $L_{mech} = 10^{38} \text{ erg s}^{-1}$. The resultant expanding shell is dense and cools down rapidly in both calculations. The inner edge of this shell coincides with the contact discontinuity. Here the density jumps from a low value in the shocked wind zone where the gas temperature is large to the much larger value in the ionized shell with a much lower (10^4 K) temperature whereas the thermal pressure does not change. The second noticeable jump in the density distribution marks the outer edge of the ionized part of the shell. The outer side of the shell remains neutral as the number of the ionizing photons is not sufficient to photoionize the whole shell. The density in the neutral segments grows for two orders of magnitude as the gas temperature drops from 10^4 K in the inner ionized part of the shell to 10^2 K in the neutral skin.

Fig. 1: The distribution of density and thermal pressure in the wind-blown shell exposed to the radiation from the central cluster and its location on the diagnostic diagram proposed in Yeh & Matzner (2012). The left-hand and right-hand upper and middle panels present the results for models A and B at different evolutionary times, $t = 1$ Myr (upper panels) and $t = 3.3$ Myr (middle panels), respectively. Solid lines on these panels correspond to the radial density distribution. Dashed and dotted lines show the distribution of thermal and ram pressure, respectively. The bottom panels display the evolutionary tracks of model A (solid lines) and B (dashed lines) on the diagnostic diagram which allows us to discriminate between the thermal and radiation pressure dominated regimes.

In the bottom two panels of the figure we plot our results on the diagnostic diagram proposed in Yeh & Matzner (2012) which allows us to discriminate between the wind and radiation-dominated regimes. The two-dimensional parameter space in this diagram is related to the compactness of the H II region (parameter Ψ) and to the relative strength of different driving forces (parameter Ω). If the ionized shell is thin, parameter Ω measures the wind dynamical over the radiation pressure ratio. The negative and positive values of $\log \Omega$ indicate whether the star cluster radiation or mechanical pressure dominates the expansion.

One can note that in the leaky/momentum-dominated bubble model the enhancement of thermal pressure inside the wind-blown shell provided by radiation pressure remains small (the upper and middle left-hand panels) and the shell evolves in the wind-dominated regime ($\log \Omega > 0$, solid lines on the bottom panels). This implies that the impact of radiation pressure on the shell dynamics is not significant in this case. In the calculations with a low (10%)

heating efficiency it is different. In this case the evolutionary track (dashed lines in the bottom panels) passes through the lower left corner in the $\Omega - \Psi$ diagram where $\log \Omega < 0$. This implies that in the low heating efficiency case the shell evolves in the radiation pressure dominated regime for a sufficiently long period of time and thus radiation may change the post-shock pressure, the leading shock speed and the shell dynamics significantly.

The calculations presented here complement those provided in Martínez-González, Silich & Tenorio-Tagle (2014) and Silich & Tenorio-Tagle (2013) for more massive ($10^6 M_{\odot}$) clusters and show that radiation pressure may affect the dynamics and inner structure of the wind-driven shell only during the earliest stages of the bubble evolution or if a significant fraction of the star cluster mechanical luminosity is dissipated or radiated away within the star cluster volume.

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